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**Leadership Communication for Community Reader: Case Study at
Komunitas Gada Baca, West Java, Indonesia**

Objective. The Gada Membaca community is a reading park initiated by an activist for the Indonesian information literacy movement. Purpose of this research is to know how leadership communication is carried out for community reader at Komunitas Gada Membaca, West Java, Indonesia. **Methods.** This research uses a case study through qualitative approach. **Results.** The result of this research is the Gada Membaca reading garden built in the assistance of information literacy activist leader succeeded in representing this need, which became a model for other reading parks in the vicinity. Leadership communication in managing a reading garden has a strategic role. The character of the community in Indonesia in general requires assistance from a figure who has a leader character. The rise and fall of the existence of a reading parks community is much influenced by a manager who has a strong character in leading. **Conclusion** of the research is the leadership communication model needed to managing a reading garden.

Keywords: leadership communication; community reading parks; activists; information literacy; reading communities

Introduction

During the proclamation of independence of the Republic of Indonesia on August 17, 1945, 95% of the Indonesian population was still "illiterate". At that time, the national movement for the Eradication of Illiteracy (PBH) was immediately launched to make people "literate". In standard terms, "literacy" is "literate" as an adjective to the noun "literacy". Public Libraries or more precisely at that time called Taman Pustaka were established to keep people who were already "literate" able to maintain and improve their abilities. This effort to establish a public library has received appreciation from the *United Nations of Educational, Scientific, and Cultural*

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Organization (UNESCO). The award was realized in the form of assistance from library consultants who were the first to visit Indonesia (Association, 2017).

In the United States, in 1974 Paul Zurkowski, president of the *Information Industry Association* (IIA) introduced the term *Information Literacy* (IL) in his proposal to the *National Commission for Library and Information Science* (NCLIS). Since then librarians in America realized the need for skills in IL. The idea immediately went worldwide and received an international response. In 2006 *The International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions* (IFLA) published *The International Guidelines on Information Literacy*. With these IFLA guidelines, librarians in Indonesia began to introduce and teach IL concepts and techniques. A translation of the IL has been proposed with a term derived from the standard term "literacy". According to this rule, the equivalent of the word IL is "information" (Sudarsono, 2007).

TBM is an institution that provides reading materials needed by the community as a place for organizing reading and learning skills development. In addition, TBM is also a place used to obtain information for the community, especially those sourced from library materials. Library material itself is all types of reading material in various forms of media. Because of the importance of this TBM, a manager is needed, and those who become managers are those who have the dedication and technical ability in managing and implementing library services to the community. In other words, a TBM manager is a person who really has awareness and responsibility in providing library services. The objectives to be achieved with this TBM activity are to generate and increase interest in reading in order to create an intelligent society, become a forum for community learning activities, and support the improvement of the ability of new illiterates in the context of eradicating illiteracy so that those who are "literate" do not become blind and continue to develop. (Office of Archives, 2016).

Based on Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, article 26 paragraph (4), it is stated that non-formal education units consist of course institutions, training institutions, study groups, community learning activity centers, taklim assemblies, and similar educational units. The TBM program started in 1992/1993. Its presence is a renewal of the Taman Pustaka Rakyat (TPR), which was founded by Community Education in the 1950s. The TBM program aims to increase interest in reading and the reading culture of the community. Therefore, the existence of TBM is very important as a means of community learning.

On February 18, 2022, the Regent of Ciamis, Dr. H. Herdiat Sunarya laid the first brick for the construction of the Gajah Dawuan (Gada) reading parks on Jl Raya Ciamis-Cirebon Winduraja Village, Kawali District, Ciamis Regency. The construction of the Reading Garden is an initiative of the Reading Gada Community, which was founded by literacy activist Agus Munawar. The Ciamis Regent said that the Ciamis Regency Government in principle supports the development of this Reading Park because it is in line with the Ciamis Regency mission in improving the quality of human resources (Human Resources) in the area (Akbar, 2018).

Fig. 1. Greetings Literature. Regent of Ciamis, Dr. H. Herdiat Sunarya accompanied by the Literacy Mother, Hj. Kania Ernawati takes a group photo after laying the first brick for the construction of the Gada TBM in Winduraja Village, Kawali Ciamis District, Thursday, 18/02/2021.

The Regent appreciated the Gada Reading Community and the people who had participated in helping the development process of the Reading Gardens. The Regent also provided cash assistance for the construction to the activity committee. According to the Regent of Ciamis, in an interview, the development of human resources is important in realizing the welfare of the community. In the future, we will assist in the construction of the Gada Reading Gardens through the APBD budget. Meanwhile, the initiator of the Gada Reading community, Agus Munawar explained the purpose of building a reading garden as a space for community activities and learning through various reading materials. In addition, it facilitates access to information and communication technology to improve people's quality of life.

The previous literature conveys the same thing in the topic of reading garden studies from Akbar (2018) about management a Community Reading Parks (TBM). The Community Reading Garden (TBM) program is a form of government support to increase interest and love for reading in the community. This program can be accessed by non-formal education units, technical implementing units of non-formal education, associations, and unions that meet the requirements. One of the government's efforts to educate the nation's life and advance people's thinking is to build Community Reading Parks (TBM) in rural and remote areas in collaboration with parties who have the same mission. Community Reading Parks (TBM) are institutions that cultivate a love for reading in the community. They provide a room for reading, discussion, book review, writing and other activities, especially in non-formal education and are equipped with reading materials and existing infrastructure, as well as supported by the manager as a motivator. For example, the Batu-Bara district government in collaboration with PT. Inalum (Persero) build Community Reading Parks (TBM) in several rural areas in Batu-Bara district such as Community Reading Parks in Lubuk Cuik Village and Community Reading Gardens in Lalang Village.”

In one interview session, Agus Munawar said that various activities can be carried out in reading gardens, the community can easily get information, and of course, it will also have an impact on providing solutions to community problems. In addition, according to Agus Munawar, activities in reading gardens create prosperity in the community. Agus Munawar was awarded the Nugra Jasadarma Pustaloka award from the Indonesian Library for his work as a driver of information literacy through reading gardens. He explained that the Gada Reading Community was established on February 18, 2015. Gada Reading was born from a series of activities that were directly beneficial and involved the local community.

Other researchers in previous studies conveyed their research results. According to Rahayu and Fakhrudin (2019), Mentari Ceria's TBM management begins with the planning, organizing, implementation, monitoring and evaluation processes. The manager of Mentari Ceria TBM makes efforts to involve the community through motivational activities. The obstacles experienced in organizing Mentari Ceria's TBM consist of technical and non-technical obstacles.

In line with the stated above, Agus Munawar hopes that the existence of this Reading Garden can encourage the growth of new communities based on volunteerism. Another hope, according to Agus Munawar, is from relevant stakeholders to support the Gada Reading Community, added Agus. Agus also explained that the meaning of the name of the community, Gada, is a combination of place names, Gajah and Dawuan. At the location where the reading garden was built, there is a large rock and Dawuan Cimuntur is below it. Referring to the description in the background, the focus of the study is the leadership communication in the Gada Membaca Community, in this case the various efforts and strategies that Agus Munawar applies in managing the Gada Membaca Community.

Purpose of this research is to know how leadership communication is carried out for community reader at Komunitas Gada Membaca, West Java, Indonesia.

Methods

The research used case study through qualitative approach. Case study research is a method to analyze a characteristic phenomenon in the society. Subject of this research is Gada Membaca Community and the research object is leadership communication. The Gada Membaca Community is a reading unique park at Kawali, Ciamis, as a pioneer and role model for all reading park at West Java.

This research used observation, interview, and literature review as data collection technique. We observed Gada Membaca Community in the leadership communication. We interviewed head of Gada Membaca Community, Agus Munawar, and volunteers. As sampling technique, we used purposive sampling. We choosed informant through qualification experience to management the reading parks and active all the activities the reading parks. We searched and analysed literature about reading parks from website, books, journal, proceeding, and thesis. In addition, we made interview transcript, message compilation, and organize data.

Results and Discussion

Information Literacy in the Gada Baca Community

Gada Reading is a community engaged in the library. With a volunteer-based management consisting of students, young, local activists, adults. There are also members of the Gada Reading community, the majority of whom are children who are in elementary school and are directly supervised by volunteers. Although it includes members directly mentored by volunteers, this library is still open to the public, anyone can visit it.

The establishment of the Reading Gada Community is a little effort to increase the reading interest of the surrounding community to "BUKU". The existence of this community has received appreciation from the government. This was recorded in an event where the Governor of West Java registered to become a member of the Gada Baca community in Kawali, Ciamis some time ago. TBMs in West Java and in some other parts of Indonesia has grown as a learning media for

the information society (Lusiana, Yanto, Anwar, & Komala, 2019). The Reading Gada Community has become a learning media to Ciamis people.

Fig. 2. The Governor of West Java Ridwan Kamil writing on the painting canvas shortly after signing the member card of the Gada Reading Community

The signing of the Gada Reading Community (KGM) membership card was also attended by the West Java Literacy Mother Atalia Praratya Kamil, Ciamis Regent Herdiat Sunarya and Ciamis Literacy Mother Kania Herdiat (Persepsi. Media Tanggap dan Akurat, 2022).

"Improve Literacy So Ciamis, West Java, Indonesia #Champion," said West Java Governor Ridwan Kamil, who took the time to stop by the Gada Reading Community Saung in Winduraja Village, Kawali District, Ciamis Regency by motorbike, after inaugurating the new face of Situ Wangi on Saturday, February 19, 2022.

The initiator of the Gada Reading community, Agus Munawar, expressed his gratitude for the presence and willingness of the Governor of West Java and the Mother of Literacy of West Java to become members of Gada Reading.

"Thank you, Kang Emil, the presence of Kang Governor will be an inspiration and motivation for the people of Ciamis, especially the millennial generation in the East Priangan region, to increase people's interest in reading and strengthen the literacy movement. By liking reading, God willing, the quality of human life will increase," said Agus,

who had received an award from West Java Governor Ahmad Heryawan

as the best TBM manager in 2011.

To Governor Ridwan Kamil, the recipient of the Nugra Jasadarma Pustaloka award from the Indonesian Library, said that people actually want to read and participate in community involvement activities organized by the library as long as access to books is close to the community. Community involvement activities in line with the needs of the community, the support from the community who cares and the people who feel the benefits of library services are important factors for community involvement.

The literacy activist, who has also received an award from the Minister of Education and Culture as the manager of the 2012 Recreational Reading Park, explained to the journalists, that the Gada Reading Community was established on February 18, 2015. Gada Reading was born from a series of activities that benefited directly and involved the local community.

“We hope that the existence of this Reading Garden can encourage the growth of new communities based on volunteerism. We also expect support from relevant stakeholders to support the Gada Reading Community,” added Agus.

The Gada Reading Community has now used the Senayan Library Management System (SLiMS) application, making it easier to manage the member visits, the loan process and availability of books. Cards and books use QR codes to make it easier to provide services.

"Improving services to members using information technology is a must, and this is our commitment as the manager of the Gada Reading Community," said Agus Munawar, a persistent young man who also received an award from the Coca Cola Foundation Indonesia in 2017.

Agus also explained that the meaning of the name of the community, Gada, is a combination of place names, Gajah and Dawuan. At the location where the reading garden was built, the construction of which was inaugurated by the Regent of Ciamis, there is a large stone and Dawuan Cimuntur is below it. Agus Munawar shared his experience that "The literacy movement can be part of human development that can pave the way to break the chain of poverty in society."

Fig. 3. Mace Reading Community

Gol A Gong Shares Volunteering Tips to the Gada Reading Community. The agenda of the Indonesian Reading Ambassador's Literacy Safari to Ciamis Regency was complemented by a visit to the Gada Reading Community in Kawali District. Gol A Gong as Indonesian Reading Ambassador 2021-2025 and his team visited the Reading Gada Community after a Writing Workshop held at the Ciamis Regency Library and Archives Service (Fibrianti, 2021).

The arrival of Gol A Gong for the second time at the Gada Reading Community was warmly and enthusiastically welcomed by the Founder of the Gada Reading Community. Mr. Agus Munawar, Chairman of the Daily Reading Community Gada Naufalia Qisthi, and all the volunteers were present. This activity was also attended by the Reading Ambassador of Ciamis Regency, the Surawisesa Entrepreneurial Association, Kawali District, Kawali Muhammadiyah Vocational School Teachers, Kawali 1 SMAN 1 Students, and community leaders.

The event, which was held at the Reading Gada Community, was a *Sharing Session* with the Indonesian Reading Ambassador with the theme of volunteerism. The event was held in the new building of the Gada Reading Community, although the construction was still not finished. The new building, which is located on the banks of the Cimuntur River, adds to the comfort of the participants with its natural atmosphere. In fact, Gol A Gong himself felt very happy to be able to carry out activities accompanied by the sound of river water ripples.

Gol A Gong started the activity by telling about the beginning of the establishment of Rumah Dunia as a community reading park which he had set up behind his house. Gol A Gong said that a community needs a *basecamp*, volunteers, organizations, and programs. Likewise with the World House at that time. After deciding on the Rumah Dunia *basecamp* at Gol A Gong's own house, Gol A Gong recruited several students to become volunteers at Rumah Dunia. It was only after successful recruiting of volunteers that Gol A Gong created an organizational structure, whose chairman was himself, and made several programs.

While nurturing its volunteers, Gol A Gong also teaches journalism to its volunteers. Volunteers are taught to write news or articles and be published in newspapers. The writing honor then became a source of funding for Rumah Dunia. The volunteers are also taught to write literary works, such as novels, short stories, and poetry until their works become *best-sellers*. The Rumah Dunia program that has survived to this day is an oration. Oration is a program to convey something for three minutes, then the audience gives criticism and suggestions. This oration is usually held on Sunday nights.

Gol A Gong said that the important things in a community are commitment, mentor capacity, consistency, and connectivity. Gol A Gong also has his new book entitled "Gong Smash" published and made a donation to help the construction process of the 3rd floor of the Gada Baca Community building. The new building will later be used for the Gada Baca Community service whose construction involved donations from the community and concerned parties.

The event, which started at 15.45, ended around 18.00 with a group photo of all participants in front of the Gada Reading Community Building. However, continued with limited *sharing* at 19.30 to 21.00. In the limited *sharing*, there was a reader of *Balada si Roya* from Lumbung District who met Gol A Gong. Before continuing their journey to another area, Gol A Gong and his team stayed one night at the house of the Founder of the Gada Reading Community.

The presence of the Indonesian Reading Ambassador is an honor and pride for the Gada Reading Community. His passion for literacy and inspiring stories became new ammunition to boost the enthusiasm of the participants, especially the Gada Reading Community volunteers, to promote literacy in the surrounding environment.

Fig. 4. Mace Reading Community

Functions and Duties of Community Reading Gardens

Since the beginning of a library being established, regardless of the type, it has been mentioned that the library or community reading park has the main activity of collecting all sources of information in various forms, namely written (*printed matter*) and recorded (*recorded matter*) or in other forms. Then all the information is processed, packaged, and compiled to be presented to the public who are expected to be the target and the target will use the reading park. Therefore, the organization of reading gardens has certain goals and objectives to be achieved. To realize the content of the intent and achieve the goals that have been set previously, there are needed strategic steps, applicable and conceptually planned policies and concrete actions. A Community Reading Park is established or built with the intent of being:

1. A place to collect or gather information, in an active sense, the community reading park has continuous activities to gather as many sources of information as possible for collection.
2. A place to process all library materials with the help of certain methods or systems, such as registration, classification, cataloging and other completeness, either manually or using information technology facilities, making collections easy to use.

3. A place to maintain and store the collection. This means that there are activities to organize, arrange, maintain, care for the collection for it to remain neat, clean, durable, intact, complete, easy to access, not easily damaged, lost, and reduced.
4. A center for information, learning resources, research, preservation and other scientific activities. Provide services to users, such as reading, borrowing, researching, in a fast, precise, easy and inexpensive way.
5. A complete and "up to date" information place for the development of knowledge, skills, and behavior/attitudes.
6. Agents of change and agents of culture from the past, present and future. In a more essential concept, the existence and progress of the community reading garden becomes a pride, and a symbol of the civilization of human life.

The Role of Community Reading Gardens

The role of a TBM is part of the main task that must be carried out in a community reading park. Therefore, the role that must be carried out will determine and influence the achievement of the Vision and Mission to be achieved. TBM in Yanto, Rodiah, and Lusiana (2016) is an institution that acts as a facilitator community in self-development and development of community groups, especially engaged in enhancing culture reading of the society. Every reading garden that is built will have meaning if it can carry out its role as well as possible. The role relates to its existence, duties and functions. The roles that community reading parks can play include:

1. In general, community reading parks are a source of information, education, research, and preservation of the nation's cultural treasures as well as healthy, inexpensive and useful recreation areas.
2. Has the role of media or a bridge that serves to connect the sources of information and knowledge contained in the collection owned.
3. Has a role as a means to establish and develop communication between fellow users, and between the organizers of the community reading park and the community it serves.
4. Can act as an institution to develop interest in reading, love of reading, reading habits, and reading culture, through the provision of various reading materials in accordance with the wishes and needs of the community.
5. Take an active role as a *facilitator, mediator, motivator* for those who want to seek, utilize, and develop their knowledge and experience.
6. It is an agent of change, an agent of development, and an agent of human culture.
7. Act as a non-formal educational institution for community members and visitors to the community reading park. They can learn independently (*self-taught*), conduct research, explore, utilize and develop sources of information and knowledge.
8. Park officers can act as mentors and provide consultation to users or carry out *user education*, and coaching and instilling an understanding of the importance of community reading parks for many people.
9. Collect and preserve a collection of library materials so that they remain in good condition.

Community Reading Garden Volunteers

This study aims to determine the causes of volunteers leaving their jobs and managing reading gardens, the motivation of edelweiss volunteers in managing reading gardens and strategies for managing edelweiss reading gardens. The research was conducted at Edelweiss Reading Park, Kamal Village, Kalideres District, West Jakarta City for approximately 2 months from the end of February to April 2020. This research method uses qualitative research, with data collection techniques through observation, interviews and document analysis. The data sources in this study were the owner of the Edelweiss Reading Park as key informant and four edelweiss volunteers who were the managers of the reading garden as the core informants. This study resulted that: (1) The causes of volunteers leaving their previous jobs and preferring to manage Reading Gardens were due to internal and external factors that motivated volunteers. Internal factors include the thought that they as a human being should be useful to others, wish to channel one's potential, and a high social spirit. External factors include the surrounding environment, community, RT/RW administrators, and motivational factors from Volunteers' parents. (2) Edelweiss Volunteers' motivation in managing Reading Gardens is dominated by self-actualization. (3) The strategy for managing the Edelweiss Reading Gardens includes planning that begins with joint discussions, implementation of activities, programs and fund management as well as evaluation of activities as a reference for the next planning (Qotrunada Salsabillah, 2020).

Volunteers in the Reading Gada Community (KGM) are school and university students, as well as come from other communities. Every day KGM has activities assisted by volunteers as tutors. Even some volunteers from faraway areas took the time to help Agus Munawar in managing KGM. KGM volunteers can be said to have sacrificed time, energy, and funds in managing KGM. Then what is the motivation that has pushed volunteers to actively help KGM?

Humans have basic physiological needs such as protection and security, love and belonging, self-esteem, respect from others, and the need to grow (Goble, 1987). Humans in the need to grow need the nature of meaning, self-sufficiency, effortlessness, playfulness, richness, simplicity, order, justice, fullness, importance, perfection, individuality, life, beauty, goodness, and truth. When viewed from the age of the KGM volunteers, most of the KGM volunteers are still of school and university age. Volunteers have basic needs, respect, and a need to grow. KGM is a reading park that provides public space for the community. Volunteers who work at KGM have a second home as a place for community to express their feelings. In addition, volunteers have awards from KGM and the surrounding community as literacy activists. KGM is not only a place that provides library materials for the community, but a space for volunteers to continue to develop themselves.

Leadership Communication

For the past 20 years, Agus Munawar has been a literacy driver. He left a mark in the form of reading houses and communities in several places in Bandung Regency. Currently he is turning his attention to the literacy movement in his hometown, Ciamis, West Java.

Fig. 5. Agus Munawar initiated the Gada Reading Community in his hometown in Winduraja Village, Ciamis Regency, West Java

Agus migrated from Ciamis Regency to Bandung in the 1990s to study. After that, he worked and settled in Bandung. In addition to his work as a journalist, he has pioneered the literacy movement since 2000 in Arjasari Village, Bandung Regency (Napitupulu, 2020). Reading is a tradition and activity for people who want deeper knowledge, have a sense of optimism for success in education, business, government and social activities. Various literacy communities have their own uniqueness in spreading the spirit of literacy such as holding lapak or reading lesehan in the form of books, magazines, articles, and several collections of novels and comics for children, teenagers and adults. The paper focuses on how the activities of the community run and affect the community in increasing literacy. The study was conducted in the Yogyakarta Street Library literacy community that is a unity of its members who have a passion for spreading literacy and are united by the same vision.

This study discusses the survival strategy of the Kolong Ciputat TBM Community in terms of social capital and social networks. The aim of this community is to increase interest in reading and educate the community, especially children in the Ciputat area, South Tangerang. The purpose of this discussion is to analyze how the survival strategy applied by the Kolong Ciputat TBM Community serves its aim. In addition, it provides an overview of what obstacles were found when implementing the survival strategy by this community. Qualitative research is used in this study to provide an overview and in-depth analysis. The data collection techniques consisted of interviews, observations, and literature studies. Various data, information, and facts in the field will be collected through data collection techniques. Later, the various data will be analyzed which will then draw conclusions as the final result of the study. The theoretical framework for analyzing this research is social capital and social networks as the basis for this community's survival strategy. The results showed that the survival strategy of the Kolong Ciputat TBM Community was divided into internal and external. First, the strategy is to survive internally by building trust among members through consistency and commitment. Second, the strategy is to survive externally through the participation of the local community that helps community activities. Plus the participation of several other communities as a survival strategy, such as South Tangerang OI, MAGMA, UIN Jakarta Scouts, and others. The obstacles in implementing the survival strategy

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include the inconsistency of volunteers, funding problems, and the community environment (angkot, thugs, and punk children) which sometimes hinder activities (Wibisono, 2019).

Agus Munawar has a long journey to manage TBM and becomes a magnet for volunteers to join KGM. The KGM owner himself has basic communication skills, including understanding each other, communicating thoughts accepting and supporting, and resolving conflicts (Harapan, 2014). Agus Munawar understands the potential of the community in the area where KGM was established. He believes that through literacy, the people around Kawali Ciamis will increase their awareness of reading and be able to improve the economic and cultural aspects of their community. He also opened himself to receive complaints from the public and even made a direct invitation (*door to door*).

One of the keys to KGM growing is that Agus Munawar as the owner of KGM is willing to listen to information from various sources. He openly accepts directions from practitioners, reading garden forums, and the public and communicates clearly on the KGM program. Persuasive communication media contributed to designing an effective communication strategy (Novianti et al., 2021). He is able to understand his communication opponents, especially the policy makers. Local and central officials even inaugurated KGM as one of the TBMs in Ciamis and actively participated in Community Service (PKM) activities held by practitioners and students at KGM. Agus Munawar has been trusted by regional policy makers as a literacy figure in Kawali Ciamis.

Several village and sub-district government programs in Kawali even collaborate with KGM in informing the community of a policy. Some donors have even helped the needs of the Kawali Ciamis community in improving their community skills, for example digital literacy skills for elementary school age children. However, Agus Munawar limits the realm of KGM not to touch politics. He made KGM purely built to meet the information needs of the community, not as a media for political campaigns.

Agus Munawar's work in building and improving KGM has been an inspiration to everyone. One of them is that he has empowered the community through KGM. This is in accordance with the legal leadership of empowerment, namely a leader who gives strength to others. An outstanding leader is said to be someone who is able to empower his members. In other words, a person is said to be creative if he is able to make people creative. If someone is creative for himself, then it cannot be said that someone is creative (Maxwell, 2001). The owner of KGM consistently improves the literacy level of the people of Kawali Ciamis and its surroundings. The community can use the learning facilities at KGM, and participate in KGM activities to improve their skills (Suherman, 2022).

The hallmark of leadership that empowers people is to keep up with change. Someone who leads change has an important and difficult responsibility (Yukl, 2005). Agus Munawar is able to accept changes and apply them in the community, for example changes in the use of technology in community reading parks (Saepudin, Sukaesih, & Rusmana, 2017). The use of technology in local communities is still difficult compared to urban communities. However, Agus Munawar uses technology in marketing KGM activities to the wider community, organizing information and retrieving library materials, and other activity facilities. Funds are usually the difficulty of TBM in realizing technology-based TBM activities. However, Agus Munawar was able to collaborate with various parties in overcoming the lack of funds. From this point of view, funds are not the main thing in the change. Collaboration is key in driving change in society.

Conclusion

Leadership communication for community reader: case study at Komunitas Gada Baca, West Java, Indonesia is leadership that empowers people and leads change. Agus Munawar through KGM fosters a reading interest in the Kawali Ciamis community and makes this activity to help the educational, economic, and cultural aspects of the community. One of them is that Kawali Ciamis children and adolescents have expertise or skills in helping learning at school and applying their expertise or interests. Regional leaders from the village, sub-district and regent levels have collaborated with KGM in promoting literacy in the community. This is accomplished by Agus Munawar's role in implementing changes in the pattern of community reading gardens that do not just carry out social actions but remain committed to bringing reading closer to the community. The leadership of the KGM owner has inspired TBM managers and literacy activists in other areas. Future research could examine leadership communication in other regional TBMs in West Java Province.

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Комунікаційне лідерство для читацької спільноти: приклад з практики Комунітас Gada Membaca, Західна Ява, Індонезія

Мета. Спільнота Гада Мембака – це територія для читання, ініційована активістом індонезійського руху за інформаційну грамотність. Мета цього дослідження – дізнатися, як здійснюється лідерська комунікація в читацькій спільноті в Гада Мембака, Західна Ява, Індонезія. **Методи.** У цьому дослідженні застосовано метод кейс-стаді з використанням якісного підходу. **Результати.** Результатом цього дослідження є аналіз лідерської комунікації на території читального саду Гада Мембака, побудованого за сприяння лідера-активіста з інформаційної грамотності, якому вдалося представити цю потребу, яка стала моделлю для інших читацьких парків в регіоні. Лідерська комунікація в управлінні читальним садом має стратегічну роль. Характер спільноти в Індонезії в цілому вимагає допомоги з боку особи, яка має характер лідера. На підйом і падіння існування спільноти парків для читання значною мірою впливає менеджер, який має сильний характер лідера. **Висновком** дослідження є модель лідерської комунікації, необхідна для управління парком читання.

Ключові слова: лідерська комунікація; спільноти читацьких парків; активісти; інформаційна грамотність; читацькі спільноти

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